

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

Although also this issue presents a good mix of topics, it is interesting to note how dominant networks have become for research: of the 5 papers in this issue, 3 deal with such aspects. But also the countries of origin of the authors reflect the variety that characterizes J.UCS: the authors in this issue come from 4 continents and 7 countries, with only two of those in Europe!

As usually, I'd like to take this opportunity to thank the members of our editorial board who were involved in the reviewing of the published papers and naturally also those members who reviewed all the papers that did not make it to publication. Their valuable feed-back will help the authors to improve their publication skills in the future. Finally, I'd also like to acknowledge the support of a number of internationally renown experts who have agreed to help with the review of articles whose subjects were in the centre of their research. Without the support of all reviewers, the existence of the journal would not be possible.

As far as J.UCS matters are concerned, you have already been informed about the changes in administration and financing of the journal last time: so far, a consortium of 9 research organisations will stand behind J.UCS as of 2012 and Christian Gütl, Graz University of Technology, will succeed me as the new Managing Editor. Despite these changes, the journal will continue in a very similar vain regarding its publication policy: open to all topics, open access with no submission or subscription fees, all papers reviewed by 3 reviewers, and a printed archival volume some time after a year has ended.

Enjoy reading the 5 papers! Consider submitting high-quality articles to our journal and if you are a tenured Associate Professor or above with a good publication record, do apply for a membership in our editorial board.

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer, Managing Editor
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